

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

POSTMENOPAUSAL SYNDROME AND THEIR MANAGEMENT

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 24/01/2022

Available online

05/03/2022

Keywords

Menopause,
Hot Flashes,
Sexual Dysfunction,
Depression,
Breast Cancer.

ABSTRACT

Menopause is most significant event for a woman life, carrying with it a slew of physiological changes with long-term consequences for her life. Although is transition to menopause has uncertain physiology and clinical symptoms. There are suggested there are causal relationships between menopause and a variety of manifestations and disorders. The proof for these links is changed and examined. There have been numerous theories about the symptoms that arise before, during, and after menopause. Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT) is frequently used to treat symptoms of estrogen withdrawal, including dyspareunia, hot flashes, vaginal dryness, night sweats, insomnia, however, it has not been demonstrated to help with depression or arthritis in middle age. Hormone replacement therapy doses and routes differ depending on the indication. Hormone replacement therapy complications vary depending on the regimen utilized. This article will describe these symptoms, as well as the underlying pathophysiology and treatment alternatives.

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Please cite this article in press as **Himanshi et al.** Postmenopausal Syndrome and Their Management. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2022;12(02).

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INTRODUCTION

Menopause is the loss of ovarian follicular function, which results in a permanent stop of menstruation. After a year of amenorrhoea, menopause is diagnosed, and the last menstrual period is calculated retrospectively. Race, socioeconomic level, age of menarche, and the number of preceding ovulations appear to have little effect on the age at menopause. Premature menopause is menopause that occurs before the age of 40. It could be idiopathic or related to chemicals, genetic abnormalities, or an autoimmune disease.

The menopausal transition is a period of time that begins with the beginnings of abnormal menstrual cycles and ends with the final menstrual flow, and it is characterized by changes in the reproductive hormones. According to current theory, perimenopause, a phase of fluctuating ovarian function, occurs 2 to 8 years before the final menses. During the menopause transition, estrogen and gonadotropins levels may be increased.¹

Vasomotor symptoms, osteoporosis, urogenital atrophy, mental symptoms, cancer, cognitive decline, cardiovascular disease, and sexual issues are the most common health concerns among menopausal women. Postmenopausal syndrome is associated with many symptoms, including Hot flashes, mood swings, irritability, dry vagina, insomnia, mental confusion, genitourinary symptoms/sexual dysfunction, poor sleep, etc.

Pathophysiology

Menopause is an ovarian failure (primary) that is connected with the modification in the pituitary and hypothalamic hormones that control menstruation. Menopause is not a central occurrence. The ovarian follicle level is decreased. As a consequence of the incapacity of the ovaries to respond to pituitary hormones for example follicle-stimulating hormone and luteinizing hormone, ovarian estrogen, and progesterone synthesis are inhibited. Due to the preservation of the stromal compartment, after menopause androgen production continues. The peripheral aromatization of ovarian and adrenal androgens continues to result in low levels of circulating estrogens in menopausal women. Obesity causes many of the symptoms of menopause because aromatization occurs in the adipose tissue. Follicle-stimulating hormone levels in the absence of negative feedback from the ovary, cells proliferate in response to ovarian failure. Lower production of estrogen and inhibin comes from atresia of the follicular apparatus, especially the granulosa cells, ensuing in decreased inhibin ranges and higher follicle-stimulating hormone levels, a crucial sign of menopause.²

Vasomotor symptoms:

Up to 75% of perimenopausal women experience vasomotor symptoms. Most women experience symptoms for 1–2 years after menopause, while some may experience symptoms for up to 10 years or more. The vasomotor symptom is a type of temperature dysregulation caused by changes in gonadal hormones.

Hot flashes:

A feeling of acute warmth is known as a hot flash that is often redness and sweating are common side effects. Hot flashes are a typical symptom of perimenopause.

Postmenopausal women up to 50% get hot flashes syndrome. According to research of the MWHP (Melbourne Women's Health Project), research that included 438 women, 5.2 years are average duration of menopausal hot flashes. Up to 25% of women experience menopausal hot flashes for up to 5 years. A meta-analysis survey which includes 35445 women found that hot flashes last for 4 years, the most uncomfortable symptoms appear approximately a year before the last menstrual period and gradually fade.

Pathophysiology of hot flashes:

Hot flashes have a complex pathophysiology. As a result of the variations or lack of estrogen production, the thermoregulatory system is assumed to be resetting and constricting. Hot flashes are thought to be caused by changes in estrogen and FSH levels as well. It could possibly be linked to the hypothalamus' upregulation of the 5-HT_{2A} receptor in response to lower serotonin levels. The reduction is assumed to be caused by lower estrogen levels.

Treatment of hot flashes:

These are reduced by estrogens, and there is a dose-dependent correlation between oestrogen dosage and the suppression of hot flashes.

There are alternatives to estrogen when it is contraindicated. For some women, progestin treatment alone is a possibility. Vasomotor symptoms are adequately treated with MPA (medroxyprogesterone acetate) (20 mg daily) and megestrol acetate (20 mg twice a day). Agents that lower central noradrenergic tone relieve hot flashes. In randomized, placebo-controlled trials, clonidine has been shown to drastically reduce vasomotor symptoms. It can be taken by oral or by transdermal route.

Hot flushes can also be relieved with SSRIs (selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors). The US FDA give approval to paroxetine (non-hormonal drug) to treat menopausal hot flashes. The paroxetine group saw a 62% reduction in composite scores hot flush, compared to 38% in placebo group. With paroxetine, the hot flushes number per day dropped by 3.3, compared to 1.8 with placebo. In a controlled experiment, venlafaxine dramatically decreased hot flushes. The venlafaxine group experienced a 61% reduction in hot flushes, compared to a 27% reduction in the placebo group. In a placebo-controlled, randomized, crossover trial, a small amount of Vitamin E (800 IU/day) reduced hot flushes.³

Urogenital atrophy:

The symptoms are observed by about 60% of women. Vaginal atrophy, sexual dysfunction, and urethral atrophy, are some of the signs and symptoms. Dryness, pruritus, and dyspareunia are symptoms of vaginal atrophy (painful intercourse). Stress incontinence, urgency, frequency, and dysuria are all signs of urethral atrophy. Urinary tract infections, as well as painful urination, are possible side effects.

Vaginal atrophy:

Women with vaginal dryness, dyspareunia, irritation, and itching, usually display evidence of epithelial pallor, vaginal atrophy, friability, and petechiae are examples of these symptoms. In the absence of symptoms, on investigation, indications of atrophy may be seen; conversely, women may have symptoms but no atrophy. As a result, the vaginal atrophy syndrome is unclear and can contain only symptoms and signs.

Treatment of vaginal atrophy:

When applied 1–3 times weekly, low-doses of estrogen cream are beneficial. Estradiol vaginal tablets are placed twice a week and are easier to use than estrogen cream. In the context of urogenital atrophy, lubricants provide a non-hormonal choice for minimizing intercourse pain. Polycarbophil (Replens) lowers vaginal pH and relieves vaginal atrophy symptoms.⁴

Sexual dysfunction:

Sexual dysfunction is caused by a variety of factors. Sexual dysfunction can be improved by treating hot flashes, mood swings, and vaginal dryness. A decreasing level of androgen is blamed for some of the manifestations, particularly in the menopause after surgery. In dyspareunia, low-dose of vaginal oestrogen and dehydroepiandrosterone can be administered.

Hormone therapy for sexual complaints:

Treatment of dyspareunia in women with vaginal atrophy is not controversial. So, it is unknown whether another oestrogen medication improves satisfaction, orgasm, arousal, or sexual desire. Vaginal secretions, vasocongestion, and effects on sensation may occur as oestrogen increases the integrity of vaginal tissue, leading to increased arousal. Many women and couples with sexual dysfunction benefit from exercises and specific activities carried out in the supervision of a therapist.

It's unclear whether testosterone has a role in sexual dysfunction, particularly low desire. Women who had an oophorectomy and received large levels of testosterone found that testosterone increases sexual desire. One study found that methyltestosterone (in combination with equine estrogens) increased self-stimulation.

Urinary tract infection:

There is no direct correlation between UTI (urinary tract infection) and menopause, after menopause some physiological changes raise the risk of infection. These alterations include a rise in pH of vagina and a change in flora vagina.⁵

Osteoporosis:

Osteoporosis causes musculoskeletal symptoms such as pain, fractures from minor trauma, decreased height, and mobility. Osteoporosis affects more than 250,000 women. Osteoporosis is characterized by loss of bone or decrease in bone density, which is caused by oestrogen insufficiency in these women. At the rate of 0.3–0.5%, women lose their bone every year once they reach the age of 40. During menopause, women lose 3% to 5% of their bone density per year for 5 to 7 years. Anovulation, chronic renal disease, hyperparathyroidism, hyperthyroidism, and diseases which require systemic corticosteroid usage are all medical factors linked to an increased risk of osteoporosis.

Treatment of osteoporosis:

Diet of many women are lacking in calcium and vit. D, and other diet modifications and supplements will help them. This can be accomplished by food or supplementation with vitamins and minerals.

Osteoporosis can be prevented and treated with hormone therapy. Oestrogen therapy has been demonstrated to prevent osteoporosis-related fractures by about 50% in observational studies. Recent research has shown that very low-dose oestrogen therapy (conjugated equine oestrogen with MPA 1; transdermal estradiol; estradiol), when combined with Vitamin D and calcium they increase bone density.

Bisphosphonates, such as alendronate, ibandronate (150 mg monthly), and risedronate (35 mg weekly), suppress resorption of bone particularly and are effective in prevention and therapy of osteoporosis.

SERMs (selective oestrogen receptor modulators) are chemicals that, depending on the tissue, operate as both oestrogen agonists and antagonists. Raloxifene (60 mg) is a SERM (selective oestrogen receptor modulator) that has been licenced for the treatment of osteoporosis. Another FDA-approved medication for osteoporosis is calcitonin nasal spray (200 IU).⁶

Depression

Several longitudinal population-based investigations have found no link between depression and the menopause transition. Symptoms of depression are increased throughout menopause transition and reduced following menopause, according to the Penn Ovarian Aging Study, a cohort study. A prior history of depression, as well as variations in reproductive hormone levels linked to low mood, were the most powerful predictors of depressed mood.

In contrast, one Canadian cohort study found that menopausal women have high rates of depressive symptoms: Over the course of three years of research, 51% of women tested positive on the CES-D (Centers for Epidemiologic Studies) Depression Scale at least once. Two more cohort's studies from the United States and the United Kingdom discovered a higher risk of menopausal depression, and mostly seen in women who had previously experienced depression. These results confirm a vulnerability theory: women having history of affective disease may be more vulnerable to mood disturbances after menopause.⁷

Pathophysiology:

Estrogen levels fluctuate and decline during perimenopause, which may contribute to depression. Estrogen and other steroid hormones act on the CNS through a variety of methods. For example, they enhance neurotransmitter production, receptor expression, and permeability of membrane. Estrogen enhances the effects of norepinephrine and serotonin; these neurotransmitters are linked to depression's physiology.

Estrogen inhibits the breakdown of serotonin and norepinephrine through decreasing MAO (monoamine oxidase) activity in the central nervous system, among other things.

Estrogen also enhances norepinephrine activity, possibly via inhibiting the enzymes catechol-O-methyltransferase and MAO, which reduces reuptake and breakdown.

Estrogen also promotes serotonin production, activates 5-HT₁ (5-hydroxytryptamine) receptors, suppresses 5-HT₂ receptors.

The exact mechanism for depression is unknown, changes in norepinephrine and serotonin modulation may occur as estrogen level change, contributing to the depression. Oestrogen aids the effects of norepinephrine and serotonin; a decreased oestrogen levels could cause a decline in these hormone levels. Changes in estrogen levels linked to symptoms of depression in certain women during the menopause.⁸

Hormonal changes:

Women's hormonal changes appear to be linked to depression. In the postpartum period and menopause transition, mood changes and hormone changes are encountered, which are regarded to the premenstrual depressive disorders. It's important to remember that gonadal hormone levels aren't linked to depression in absolute terms. Progesterone and Estrogen levels don't distinguish between depressed and non-depressed women. Hormone concentrations in the peri- and postmenopausal women with depressive symptoms were not observed to be abnormal. During perimenopause depression seems to be more common, when level of hormones is fluctuating, than after menopause, when level of oestrogen and progesterone is low but constant.

Treatment of depression:

Antidepressants known as SSRIs are the most widely prescribed medications for perimenopausal depressive disorders. Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors are regarded to be efficient and safe in the vast majority of cases. They can cause serotonin syndrome, as well as intestinal problems (nausea, diarrhoea, and anorexia), increased akathisia, sweating, jitteriness, sleeplessness, dizziness, sedation and decreased libido.

HRT alone may be sufficient for mild depression. When standard antidepressants fail, individuals refuse psychiatric medicines, or patients develop other clinically significant vasomotor symptoms, oestrogen (conjugated oestrogen, medroxyprogesterone) may be utilised.

Several studies found that oestrogen replacement therapy in perimenopausal women had antidepressant effects or increased the benefits in treatment of antidepressants. Some studies show that oestrogen has an antidepressant effect only in women who have vasomotor symptoms. However, the majority of evidence suggests that oestrogen show no beneficial effect on mood or quality of life in healthy women without depression. Menopause anxiety appears to be linked to higher chances of depression and physical manifestation of menopause. Anxiety, depression, and irritability are reduced in women who participate in educational groups that assist them understand what to expect throughout menopause.⁹

Insomnia:

Menopause appears to bring an additional, difficulty to this progressive process of insomnia. By actigraphy and by self-report, found that near the time of menses sleep is worse, as women progress through the menopausal transition. According to actigraphy research, a women loss up to 25 minutes of sleep per night in her late reproductive years. During the menopausal transition, 40–50% of women experience insomnia, and sleep problems may or may not be linked to mood disorders. Sleep problems in women can be caused by a variety of causes, including depression, smoking, lack of physical activities, and anxiety. Despite the fact that vasomotor symptoms are linked to higher waking and poor sleep quality, late peri- and postmenopausal women still have higher sleep problems than menopausal women, independent of the existence of vasomotor disorders.

Hormonal changes are unlikely to be the only cause of sleep problems during menopause. Hormones do not always work to cure sleep issues in midlife and beyond, which supports this theory. Sleep issues are exacerbated by poor sleep hygiene habits and emotional disorders.

Treatment:

On the therapy of menopausal sleep disruption, there are various clinical trials and review studies. Because hormone replacement therapy lowers oestrogen levels, which are linked to vasomotor symptoms in perimenopause, and vasomotor symptoms are closely linked to chronic insomnia, it has the potential to help both vasomotor symptoms and chronic insomnia. Estrogen treatment enhances sleep quality by reducing heart failure and night-time awakenings. Oral progesterone shows sedative effect, most likely due to its GABA-agonistic activity, in that it suppresses wakefulness without impairing daytime function.

The Selective estrogens, Menopause and Response to Therapy (SMART) studies investigated and compared bazedoxifene/conjugate oestrogen to the placebo in a double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled experiment. At 3 months, bazedoxifene resulted in significant decrease in heart failure frequency, as well as improvements in health-related quality of life and sleep metrics as compared to placebo. Antidepressants, such as trazodone and mirtazapine, have been studied as therapies for menopausal insomnia, although they are not authorized by FDA for treatment of insomnia. In the absence of depression, antidepressants are not recommended for the frequent usage in menopausal sleeplessness.¹⁰

Breast tenderness:

Breast discomfort is more common in the early phases of perimenopause, and the severity of the symptoms decreases with age. Breast tenderness can also arise as a result of HRT (hormone replacement treatment), and it can happen if the circulating amount of estrogen suddenly rises.

Restless legs:

This syndrome is a frequent ailment that occurs primarily at night. Female sex hormones play a major role in the increased prevalence of syndrome in women and, as a result, the severity of the condition throughout the female life cycle. 69% of individuals in one research said their symptoms worsened after menopause.¹¹

Dementia:

After the survey, found that dementia occur in females more as compare to males. Dementia is major cause of death, more than cancer. Some female experience forgetfulness or other cognitive symptoms throughout the natural menopause, which can raise concerns about mental decline. As a result, several researchers have studied on the role of oestrogen in dementia risk. In the brain oestrogen interact with serotonergic and cholinergic system, which are both important for appropriate cognitive function. Higher verbal memory performance was observed in premenopausal women during the menstrual cycle phases linked with high oestrogen level.

Neuritic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles characterise Alzheimer's disease, which is the most frequent reason of dementia. The dissemination of aberrant, is a prominent feature. Alzheimer's alterations are frequently discovered at autopsy alongside other pathologies that cause dementia. Infarction, Lewy bodies, and TDP-43 inclusions are examples of these (frontotemporal dementia).¹²

Thyroid dysfunction:

Many indications of menopause are identical to those associated with thyroid disease. It can be difficult to tell the difference between thyroid disease and menopause symptoms because they are so similar. Thyroid disorder is widespread, particularly among women over 50 years old. Observe the symptoms of thyroid illness with age when caring for perimenopause and postmenopausal women. Osteoporosis and cardiovascular disease are more common in postmenopausal women, and their risks are compounded by undiagnosed thyroid disease.¹³

Cardiovascular Disease:

When women reach menopause, the incidence rises at a faster rate than it does in men. The decrease in oestrogen during menopause affects not just vasoconstriction. In fact, people who have achieved menopause have a 2 to 3 times higher risk of coronary heart disease than those who have not. As a result, menopausal women are recommended to eat well and exercise regularly to reduce the risk factors. Other biochemical pathways, including endothelin levels, oxidative stress, plasma renin, and sympathetic nervous system activity contribute to a rise in hypertension during menopause. Vasomotor tone change, arterial remodelling, arterial stiffness and inflammation ensue from endothelial dysfunction, contributing to target damage of organ and atherosclerosis.

Treatment:

Studies evaluating the relationship between unopposed oestrogen use and the risk of coronary heart disease events consistently demonstrate that postmenopausal women who use oestrogen had lower rates of events than non-users. When oestrogens are taken with progestagens, the lipid benefit is mitigated to some extent, it is depended on kind and dose of progestagen. Conjugated oestrogens generated the largest rise in high density lipid in the Postmenopausal Estrogen Intervention Trial. In comparison to conjugated equine oestrogens alone, a combination of conjugated oestrogens plus micronized progesterone shows a slightly lower rise in high density lipid. The third biggest increase in HDL was seen with this combo regimen. In women with hypertension, hormone treatment does not elevate blood pressure.¹⁴

Vascular dysfunction:

Endothelial dysfunction is included in vascular dysfunction and massive arterial stiffness, is linked to ageing. The vascular endothelium is a single layer cell that lines artery walls and becomes these walls dysfunctional as people age, in part because of decreased nitric oxide (NO) availability as a result of increasing oxidative stress and inflammation. The vascular function preserved in women until the menopausal transition, after menopause it deteriorates gradually, presumably due redox balance and inflammatory condition. The reduction of E₂ antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities has been linked to pro-inflammatory and pro-oxidant conditions in postmenopausal women. Women who were perimenopausal or postmenopausal had higher artery stiffness, as showed by an increase in PWV (pulse wave velocity) and decrease in carotid artery.¹⁵

Cardiac dysfunction:

Vascular dysfunction can lead to modifications in pathophysiology of the heart that rise risk of cardiovascular disease in conjunction with a change in body composition. Increased systolic rate and pressures of pulses, as well as aortic impedance can result in an increase in afterload and the volume of labour required by the left ventricle to eject the blood. Left ventricle hypertrophy, and a decrease in left ventricle systolic reserve can all result from these alterations. OVX mice study show that acquired left ventricle hypertrophy and were restored by E₂ replacement provide evidence for estrogens function in LV hypertrophy generated by pressure overload. Women's LV mass increases as they age, resulting in higher diastolic dysfunction when compared to men.¹⁶

Hypertension:

Increases in BP and the prevalence of hypertension have been linked to menopause in a few studies. Menopause is linked to a drop in BP in several studies. According to two population-based longitudinal studies of women in their forties, the transition from premenopausal to postmenopausal status was not associated with distinct changes in blood pressure, glucose, or insulin levels.

Palpitations:

It is an unpleasant sensation caused by an irregular heartbeat. This symptom can be caused by a range of cardiac illnesses, including CAD (coronary artery disease) valvular heart disease and cardiomyopathy, but primary cardiac arrhythmias are the most common cause. Palpitations can be caused by noncardiac situations, and in this case reflect a consequence of the disease on cardiac rhythm.

Women of all ages have palpitations, which are more common during pregnancy, the luteal phase of menstrual cycle, and perimenopausal era. It is more common in perimenopausal women, these are harmless, and are linked to the higher sympathetic activity brought on by menopause. Palpitations have been linked to a decrease in quality of life.¹⁷

Obesity:

Obesity, particularly visceral (android) obesity, becomes more common after menopause. Such fat distribution promotes the development of atherosclerosis and promotes metabolic diseases. Up to two-thirds of menopausal women in Poland are overweight. This weight gain during menopause has been investigated as a possible primary contributor to midlife body weight. Men of the same age have shown a similar increase in adiposity, showing that chronologic ageing rather than reproductive ageing is to blame. Obese women showed lower levels of estradiol (E₂) and follicular stimulating hormone (FSH) in the POAS (Penn Ovarian Aging Study), as well as lower levels of inhibin B and LH in the POAS. Postmenopausal women had more whole body and intra-abdominal fat. After accounting for fat percentage, fat mass, and plasma glycerol levels remained consistent. Furthermore, when pre- and postmenopausal women were matched for intra-abdominal fat and fat mass, no variations observed in plasma glycerol. Under postabsorptive or hyperinsulinemic situations, their findings suggested that menopausal status had little effect on plasma glycerol levels. The hormones leptin and resistin are raised in menopausal women, while adiponectin and ghrelin are decreased. Excess fat in postmenopausal women causes an increase in endogenous oestrogen synthesis.¹⁸

Hyperandrogenism:

It is a state of absolute or relative androgen excess caused by ovaries and adrenals, which is significantly indicated by the emergence or rise in hair growth, as well as development of virilization signs and symptoms. Years after menopause, the ovary remains hormonally active, and secretes considerable levels of androgens and few estrogens. Although oestrogen levels drop suddenly after menopause, androgen secretion decreases over time and is maintained until later in life. LH stimulation stimulates androgen secretion in menopausal women; after menopause, ovarian androgen secretion is maintained by high gonadotropin level despite significant oestrogen loss.

Treatment:

Patients with hyperandrogenism diagnosed with antiandrogens like cyproterone acetate, spironolactone, and flutamide. The effect of metformin is unknown, it is beneficial in the insulin-resistant hyperandrogenic women who also follow a healthy diet and exercise routine, especially if they are obese. The treatment for iatrogenic hyperandrogenism is to stop using the drug or supplement. Bilateral oophorectomy or GnRH analogues can be used to treat hyperandrogenism caused by OH; this treatment has been demonstrated to reduce symptoms and may alleviate concurrent metabolic problems. Patients with advanced disease may require mitotane and chemotherapy as an adjuvant treatment.¹⁹

Breast Cancer:

In 2012, 6.7 million women were diagnosed with cancer worldwide, out of a total of 14.1 million. In 2035, the overall population is predicted to reach 24 million. The most frequent cancer is breast cancer. With the exception of cervical cancer, cancer rates in industrialised countries are 1.8 times greater than in developing countries. The breast cancer rises after menopause in The United States, but rises before or during menopause in Asia. Cancer mortality rates vary by type and area of the world, although they generally rise with age. In countries with a nationwide screening programme, mortality due to breast cancer has fallen significantly. Mammography is advised for women between the ages of 50 and 74. Screening for women have higher risk can begin earlier in life and be done on a yearly basis. MRI is done for women who have tested positive for BRCA1/2 mutations due to family history or for difficult-to-read mammography.

Treatment:

The link between hormone replacement therapy and breast cancer risk in women over 50 is complicated, although it is linked to oestrogen. In Women's Health Initiative (WHI), the absolute elevated risk was found 8 per 10,000 women per year. The risk is associated with late menopause, obesity, more alcohol consumption or nulliparity. Compared to medroxyprogesterone acetate and norethisterone acetate, micronised progesterone or dydrogesterone daily for 12 days shows a lower risk of breast cancer.

In a month for 12 days, cyclic regimens comprise progesterone or MPA. To minimize the side effect of nausea and tiredness. Taking progestin during night is recommended.²⁰

CONCLUSION

The menopausal transition happens when a woman's psychological, social and biological changes are coincided at a point in her life cycle. Acute symptoms such as sleep disorder, hot flashes, decreased sexual desire and mood swings may rise the difficulty of the menopausal transition.

Hormone therapy for postmenopausal women is a complicated procedure with both favourable and negative health outcomes. The benefits of oestrogen and combined therapy are reduced the dangers, according to most decision evaluations. The best Hormone replacement therapy type, mode of administration, dose and time period of therapy should all be carefully evaluated at least once a year, using the most recent published standards. One decision analysis, which took into account baseline risk factors for CHD and breast cancer, found that female with one risk factor for CHD (with breast cancer) could assumed to live longer with hormone therapy. Each woman places a different value on the different health outcomes linked with HRT. The choice to utilise HRT should be taken by the woman and practitioner, and it should take into account all potential advantages and hazards.

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